

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

Drawn in Class: What Student Desk Drawings Reveal

Mohamed TOUATI

Pioneer High School of Gabes, Tunisia

mohamedtouati.college@gmail.com

Abstract—This research aims at investigating and revealing the meanings behind student-made drawings and writings on classroom desks, often classed as mere doodles or vandalism, and reinterprets them as silent acts of self-expression, identity, resistance as well as a proof of existence. Conducted in Tunisian high school classrooms, the research includes a combination of observational data from twenty-nine desks in two schools of different social classes with informal interviews of five students. The markings differed between the two schools and they were categorized into names, quotes, symbols, and drawings, revealing recurring emotional, social, and cultural themes. Drawing on the theories of Michel de Certeau[1], James C. Scott[2], Norman Fairclough[3], and Pierre Bourdieu[4], the paper discusses that desk graffiti might be seen as a sort of everyday communication shaped by habitus, power structures, and the desire for agency. The study also touches on Marx's distinction[5] between 'class in itself' and 'class for itself,' hypothesizing that desk drawings may reflect deeper class-based inequalities in self-expression and social awareness. It further links these expressions to insights in customers behavior, where personal marks, like doodles or brands, serve as identity tools. These findings suggest that even in structured environments like classrooms, individuals find creative ways to retrieve space and voice.

I. INTRODUCTION

During long or “boring” classes, almost **70%** of students, according to informal surveys, find themselves with no consciousness drawing on their desks. These simple markings: initials, symbols, logos, and even sentences are often dismissed as meaningless distractions or acts of disfigurement. However, research suggests that doodling can be beneficial; It can, in fact, enhance memory and help individuals recall **29%** more information than those who don't doodle.[6]

But what if these acts of drawing mean more than just “idle scribbles”? What if they are silent ways for students to express identity, resist authority, or regain liberty in environments that often feel controlled or impersonal?

This paper immerses in the question: **What do the drawings on students' desks reveal about their thoughts, emotions, and behavior?**

While desk graffiti may seem random, it could be an effective method to analyze how students communicate when they feel bored, stressed, or disconnected from the world.

Some observations have been made in international studies: research in Iran[7] and Nigeria[8] found that graffiti often reflects students' emotional states, social frustrations, and cultural influences, serving as informal

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

channels of self-expression and even resistance to educational constraints

Researchers have also proven that doodling can help people, students in particular, focus or manage anxiety during extended periods of listening. In spaces like classrooms, the desk becomes a quiet canvas: a place where students leave behind traces of identity, humor, revolution, or self-reflection. In other words, students leave their prints on the desks they sit on during a whole academic year.

Inspired by the French priest **Michel de Certeau's** concept of *everyday tactics* and the American political scientist and anthropologist **James C. Scott's** theory of *hidden transcripts*, this study sees desk drawings as quiet ways students use to express themselves without breaking classroom rules.

To examine this, I visited two classrooms at two schools of different social class backgrounds and documented the markings found on desks. I started first with my school, the pioneer high school of Gabes, which is a public school with visibly old infrastructure. To expand the range of the analysis, the study was later extended to include a second classroom from a different school, the excellence private school of Gabes, with a contrasting socioeconomic background, allowing for a comparative dimension. It is, in fact, a private school with access to more resources, smaller class sizes and newer furniture.

I also made short interviews with students in order to understand their motivations and thoughts behind these drawings.

In addition to categorizing and analyzing the content, this study applies principles of **Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)**, as introduced by **Norman Fairclough (1995)**, to interpret what these inscriptions reveal about student identity, emotion, and silent resistance within the educational setting as well as **Pierre Bourdieu's**

concept of habitus and symbolic capital to pay close attention to **how students' social class influences their modes of expression.**

To start exploring this question, I informally examined the surfaces of **29 desks** in both classrooms. The markings varied: some featured **initials**, others contained **song lyrics, quotes from TV shows, emojis, or small drawings** such as mustaches or hearts.

As shown in Figure 1, names were the most frequently observed type of marking, accounting for about **45%** of all graffiti. These early observations suggested that desk drawings were not random at all — but patterned expressions of emotion, identity, and cultural references.

Figure 1. Types of drawings found on 29 student desks in two Tunisian high school classrooms. Names were the most common, followed by quotes, lyrics, and symbols.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Summary

This study was conducted in two phases: (1) observing the drawings and markings on student desks in Tunisian classrooms, and (2) conducting brief interviews with pupils to understand their motivations and interpretations of these acts.

1) Observation

The observational phase took place in two classrooms in Tunisia: one located in a school

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

...serving primarily middle-class students and another in a school serving a more economically disadvantaged population. This allowed for a comparative analysis of how social class influences the nature and themes of desk markings. The main aim was to analyze potential meanings of the drawings found on desk surfaces during regular school days. Data collection was carried out informally, outside of class hours, to avoid interrupting lessons and to ensure ethical, unobtrusive research.

Each desk was visually inspected and all visible markings were noted. Observations focused on the **type, size, placement, and content** of each drawing or written element. These markings were then grouped into different categories:

- **Names or initials**
- **Quotes and song lyrics**
- **Symbols and emojis**
- **Doodles or drawings** (e.g., hearts, mustaches).

Prior international research, such as the Iranian and Nigerian studies on student graffiti, which analyzed content differences between urban and rural schools or schools of varying resources inspired the comparative aspect of this research.

This categorization emphasized symbolic and expressive content rather than artistic quality. The two settings were chosen purposefully to reflect differences in social context. Despite these differences, the presence of desk markings was prevalent in both environments ;though, their styles, themes, and frequencies varied

To protect student privacy and respect the ethical standards, no identifying information was recorded, and no desks were photographed. All data was only collected through observation and written notes.

Figure 2. Proportion of Desks with Drawings (n = 29)

Figure 2. Proportion of desks with drawings observed in the classrooms (n = 29). All desks contained some form of marking, indicating the widespread nature of the practice.

2) Interviews

To make the observational data even richer, **five students** from different classrooms were informally interviewed. The aim was to explore students' motivations and their personal interpretations of these acts. Each participant was asked the following three questions:

1. Why do you draw?
2. What do you usually draw?
3. How do you feel when you do it?

Responses helped provide context for interpreting the visual data, offering insight into how students see desk drawings as expressions of **boredom, identity, emotion, or playful resistance**.

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

Figure 3. Reported Reasons for Drawing on Desks (n = 5)

Figure 3. Distribution of self-reported reasons students draw on desks (n = 5). Responses included boredom (40%), self-expression (20%), fun (20%), and stress relief (20%).

B. Analysis

The collected data was interpreted through the lens of **Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)**, following **Norman Fairclough's framework** (1995), which analyzes how language and visual symbols reflect power relations, social identities, and underlying emotions.

Additionally, this study draws on:

- **Michel de Certeau's** concept of "everyday tactics" (1984), which views such acts as subtle, creative responses to structured environments.
- **James C. Scott's** theory of "hidden transcripts" (1990), which explores how dominated groups express dissent in indirect, concealed forms.
- **Pierre Bourdieu's** theories on habitus and social capital, which also inform the analysis by highlighting how social class and cultural backgrounds shape students' practices of self-expression.

Together, these frameworks allow us to treat desk drawings not as random graffiti, but as **meaningful acts** of communication and

self-expression shaped by power, class, culture, and resistance within the controlled space of the classroom.

III. RESULTS

The observational and interview phases of this research both helped reveal key patterns in the **content** and **possible functions** of desk drawings.

A. Ubiquity and Variety of Markings

Out of the 29 desks observed, **100% contained markings**. However, differences were observed between the two schools. In the private school, drawings tended to be neater, with more frequent use of English-language quotes, brand references, or personal mottos, whereas in my school, the observed markings were more emotionally charged or political in tone; they included lyrics in Arabic as well as slang expressions, hearts with names, and references to family or local identity .

This widespread presence suggests that desk graffiti is not an isolated behavior but rather a **common practice** among students (see **Figure 2**).

The markings were grouped into four dominant categories:

- **Names or initials** (found on 13 desks): These appeared in stylized fonts or surrounded by hearts and stars, possibly in order to reflect identity, friendship bonds, or romantic feelings.
- **Quotes and song lyrics** (7 desks): Frequently referencing popular media or music, these writings could reflect students' emotional states, taste, or attempts at self-expression.
- **Symbols and emojis** (4 desks): Common symbols included peace signs, hearts, smiley faces, and musical notes; they are quick to draw, yet rich in emotional tone.

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

- **Doodles and abstract drawings** (5 desks): From mustaches to geometric shapes, these ranged from humorous to artistic, often with no text.

Some desks included more than one category, showing that a student might have several reasons for doodling all at once.

Figure 4. A classroom showcasing student desks heavily marked with drawings, symbols, and writings.

B. Student Perspectives: Why Draw?

Interviews with five students shed light on their motivations. When asked why they (or others) draw on desks, answers were surprisingly candid and reflective. The most common reason was **boredom**, followed by **self-expression**, **fun**, as well as **stress relief**.

All five participants were informed about the study's purpose and agreed to be named and quoted in the final paper.

Most of the answers showed that the main motivation behind drawing is "To feel less stressful as well as to leave traces and prints for next generations", mentioned that students usually draw "flowers or emojis" and write their "initials or song lyrics" and those students

admitted that they feel nothing doing it "Nothing honestly it's just a waste of time" they said.

Yet, a pioneer high school of Gabes student, Fatma BARDI, had a different answer to those three questions .

She said "Sometimes it feels like just drawing is already making art, and if you look at the word "art", its Greek root 'techne' means a kind of know-how or craft. Besides, if you ask me why and what I draw? I'd simply say: to free myself from everything around me, to escape reality, or maybe to go far away to meet my unconscious, where I might find answers to so many questions!

And when it comes to answering the question: what do I draw? Usually eyebrows haha, eyes, I write people's names, quotes, or cartoon characters When I do it, I feel disconnected; I don't hear anything, I'm not analyzing anything. I don't know why, but I'm doing something. Whether I like it or not... I didn't even know. And well, you're asking me things I'm trying to answer for the first time! I feel alone, but in a good way, maybe because it's just me, my beautiful creations, and my thoughts and that's enough for me, actually. I'm creating something that reflects who I am, something that comes from me, and it's the only place where I feel 100% myself"

Those reasons are shown in **Figure 3**. Although on a small scale, this feedback supports the idea that these markings are more than just distractions; they function as subtle emotional or strategies students depend on to cope with the classroom environment.

C. Class-Based Differences in Desk Expression

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

schools	private	public
<i>Visual tone</i>	Neat	rough
<i>Language</i>	English	Arabic
<i>Themes</i>	Global pop	Emotion and personal identity
<i>Symbols</i>	Branded logos	handwritten quotes or initials

This difference is a reflection of the different cultural capital (mentioned by Bourdieu) available to students in each setting. In private schools, students may draw more from globalized media and consumer imagery, however, in public schools, expression may be related to local concerns and personal emotions.

D. Interpretive Themes: Hidden Voices and Everyday Tactics

Based on **Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 1995)**, we can interpret that the markings reveal **unspoken narratives**. They display a tension between the strict rules, quiet atmosphere, and pressure to fit in at school on one side and the student's urge to **prove existence and assert humor** on the other.

In a strict as well as controlled classroom, drawing on desks gives students the ability to take back a tiny piece of their freedom.

Agreeing on **Michel de Certeau's** theory "everyday tactics", desk graffiti becomes an improvisational practice of **disobedience** or **presence** and considered as a whisper beneath the teacher's voice.

In the same way, citing **James C. Scott's** concept "hidden transcripts", these markings can be seen as an alternative communication way, through which students express what they can't say out loud such as fatigue, affection, boredom, and even objection.

E. Synthesis

Since **every desk had drawings**, this habit is not exceptional. In fact, it is very common between students who often have no clue about the deeper meaning their behaviour contains, yet, their traces are means to communicate and assert resistance in silence.

Additionally, the desks drawings which were grouped into four main categories, work as mirrors of learners' **emotions, identities** as well as **expressions**.

Moreover, exploring those markings through new perspectives, such as sociological or language based sides, gives them a meaning, revealing that they extend from being just doodles to being **rich texts** of classroom life.

IV. Context and Theoretical Framework

It is admitted that social structure in France is shaped by not just numerous but also connected factors that have a crucial influence on individuals' positions, identities as well as their means of expression; and that was remarked in the desk drawings in this study.

Indeed, Classical sociological theories, such as those of Marx, Weber[9], and Bourdieu, are still relied on in order to understand how social classes last and develop.

For instance, the concept of classes in themselves and for themselves Karl Marx talked

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

about, spots the light on the everyday living conditions and the increasing awareness that define class dynamics, whereas Pierre Bourdieu talks and focuses on the role economic, cultural, and symbolic capital play in maintaining social hierarchies: how people are ranked among society.

Since the decline of the “Trente Glorieuses,”:the thirty years of economic strength and increasing living standards in France after the second world war, social inequalities have become deeper and the gap has grown , particularly between a powerful “bourgeoisie”, in which hands wealth became more concentrated, and increasingly precarious popular classes who faced more and more financial hardships and instabilities. Although it has become more challenging for them to remain united, their frustrations and awareness of unfair treatment still come through in social movements such as the “gilets jaunes” (yellow vests).

However,as time passes, the traditional boundaries of class have become blurred, and that is partially due to processes called “moyennisation” in France:the growth of a large middle class as well as the reduction of the differences between the upper and working classes.

At the same time,new Sociodemographic factors such as gender, age, and ethnicity have become sometimes even more important than the class itself in shaping individuals’ life experiences as well as identities.

For example, employment categories known as PCS are linked to cultural capital and access to resources, yet, gender[10] inequalities still exist in salaries, job division, and domestic responsibilities.

In reality,geographic inequalities actually worsen those gaps, since people who live in poor neighborhoods lack access to quality education, good healthcare, and employment; therefore, those factors create a complicated social framework in which young people’s expressions, like drawings on desks,might present reflections of their multifaceted social positions and resistance to dominant layers.

For a fact, realizing that society is shaped by different factors helps understand better and see

these acts as silent ways of self-expression. It also highlights the importance of looking at social behavior in a more complete way, rather than focusing only on social classes.

The variety and differences in the desk drawings between the two classes mirrors models of cultural as well as symbolic capital; in fact,students coming from different social classes tend to express their identities through different repertoires shaped by being exposed to cultural norms, media, and school expectations. This interpretation agrees with Bourdieu’s view that habitus is conditioned by social class.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A.Discussion

To begin with, all desks containing markings among all the observed ones proves nothing but that drawing on such school furniture is not an exceptional nor isolated act,instead it is considered as widespread and highly common between students.

Although those markings were always seen as just meaningless doodles,they may actually hold emotional, social, and psychological backgrounds behind that.

The observation of two socially contrasting schools revealed how class conditions not only provide access to resources, but also affect the ways in which students express themselves. It is true that both sets of students engaged in the act of drawing,however, their content differed;that suggests that even small acts like doodling are certainly shaped by larger social structures and forms of cultural conditioning.

In the context of **Michel de Certeau’s** theory of everyday tactics, the act of drawing can be seen as a **method of regaining space** in an environment controlled and full of rules, schedules, and expectations. The desk,known typically as a symbol of order, discipline, and institutional learning, becomes here a personal canvas where students assert their presence in powerful ways.

Similarly, drawing can be seen, using **James C. Scott’s** concept of the “**hidden transcript**”, as

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

a way students communicate feelings or ideas they might not be courageous enough to openly express. For instance, a heart drawn in the corner can translate a person's love life, a sad lyric from a pop song may describe someone's emotional state, or even a mustache scribbled under a teacher's name may reflect the feelings a student holds towards that educator. They all carry quiet messages of resistance, identity, or emotional expression. During the interviews, scholars described the act of drawing as calming, expressive, and even transformative rather mindless or disruptive and that supports the precedent approach considering this act as a form of release as well as self-reflection.

In reality, their answers agree with some psychological studies finding that **doodling can help boost focus and reduce stress** during passive tasks such as listening to long lectures. Seeing things from a **Critical Discourse Analysis** (CDA) perspective, desk graffiti is a reflection of **unspoken conversations between students and their school environment**. The desk becomes their refuge, a space where emotions, power dynamics, and identity are negotiated; they are discussed not through formal speech, but through marks, symbols, and scratches.

Furthermore, the observed desk drawings reveal not only individual strategies to cope with conditions but also reflect social inequalities and cultural differences linked to students' socio-economic backgrounds.

Indeed, learners from more privileged environments may use desk doodles to assert cultural capital or creativity, while others from less advantaged backgrounds often express subtle forms of resistance or identity affirmation shaped by their distinct "habitus".

This function strengthens how seemingly trivial acts exemplify complex social negotiations and power dynamics within the classroom, mirroring Pierre Bourdieu's theory of symbolic capital and Michel de Certeau's everyday tactics.

Seeing desk graffiti as a meaningful way of communication gives educators an opportunity with a nuanced perspective, encouraging them

to engage with these markings as windows into student identities, emotions, and social positioning, rather than simply viewing them as vandalism; and that helps them understand pupils more.

Although this study's main focus is on educational spaces, its consequences extend to **consumer behavior and marketing**.

Research consistently shows that people use visual symbols such as brand logos in order to communicate identity and status.

For instance, a Brazilian study[11] found that people tend to express themselves by highly consuming brands, linking conspicuous consumption[] directly to identity formation. Similarly, a cross-cultural study[12] proved that customers make their purchase choices based on their self-image or aspirations.

More than that, urban art[13], which is an informal form of expression like desk graffiti, is no exception; it can really influence observers' understandings of brand value and identity. Just as students draw in order to make personal signs about who they are or how they feel, consumers use products to signal identity, emotion as well as social belonging.

On the other hand, the models observed in my study resonate with findings from Iranian and Nigerian research, where graffiti was found to express social dissatisfaction, and even resistance. However, the class-based differences in the two Tunisian schools suggests that students' ways of "leaving a trace" are shaped not only by personal emotions, but also by social inequalities and culture, aligning with Bourdieu's notion of "habitus" and cultural capital.

B. Conclusion

In conclusion, student desk drawings are more than just random doodles. They are, in fact, **acts of quiet expression in silence** that deserve to be seen, studied, and understood. Far from being meaningless, these markings offer an opportunity for teachers to dive into the minds and emotions of students; those doodles reveal how they cope, resist, and express themselves in everyday academic life.

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.

In sum, the drawings on student desks are not trivial or purposeless markings but serve as rich texts reflecting the intersection of individual expression and social structure. They reveal how young people navigate institutional constraints while asserting identity and coping with social hardships. This study highlights the importance of viewing such everyday acts through a sociological lens to better understand the silent narratives rooted in school life. Future research should further explore how these expressions differ across different social, cultural, and geographic contexts to deepen our understanding of youth resistance.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank my classmates for their openness during the interviews and for allowing me to observe their desks for the purpose of this study. Their honesty and creativity made this research possible. Special thanks to the students and staff from both participating schools for granting access to their classrooms, which enabled the comparative part of this study. I also acknowledge the international research that informed my work, studies conducted in Iran and Nigeria in particular, which offered valuable cross-cultural context and inspiration. Lastly, I am deeply grateful to the theorists Michel de Certeau, James C. Scott, Norman Fairclough, and Pierre Bourdieu, whose ideas inspired me, provided the backbone for my analytical framework, and helped me reimagine ordinary drawings as meaningful social texts.

VII. ABBREVIATIONS

CDA, Critical Discourse Analysis; ID, identity; TV, Television; %, Percent; PCS, Professions et catégories socioprofessionnelles

REFERENCES

[1]De Certeau, M. (1984). *The Practice of Everyday Life*. University of California Press.

[2]Scott, J. C. (1990). *Domination and the Arts of Resistance: Hidden Transcripts*. Yale University Press.

[3]Fairclough, N. (1995). *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. Longman.

[4]Bourdieu, P. (1972). *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge University Press.

[5]Marx, K. (1867). *Capital: Critique of Political Economy*, Volume I. Penguin Classics

[6]Andrade, J. (2009). What does doodling do? *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 23(6), 960–966. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.1509>.

[7]Iranian Journal of Educational Research. (2024). *The Study of Graffiti (Wall and Desk Writings) of Junior High School Students in Tehran*. *Iranian Journal of Educational Research*, 16(2), 45–59.

[8]Journal of Humanities and Social Science (Nigeria). *Patterns of Graffiti Behaviour among In-School Adolescents in South-East Nigeria*. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 27(6), 33–40. <https://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol.27-Issue6/Series-3/E2706033340.pdf>

[9]Weber, M. (1949). *The Theory of Social and Economic Organization* (A. M. Henderson & T. Parsons, Trans.). Free Press. (Original work published 1922)

[10]De Beauvoir, S. (1949). *The Second Sex*. Vintage Books.

[11]Santos, R. M. L. & Martins, J. M. (2018). *Conspicuous Consumption and Self-Expression: The Role of Status Consumption in Brazil*. *Redalyc.Revista de Administração Mackenzie*, 19(4), 1–21. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/1230/123059410001/>

[12]Swoboda, B., & Hirschmann, J. (2016). *Brands as means of self-expression: A cross-cultural study*. University of Mannheim. Retrieved from <https://studylib.net/doc/5452623/>

[13]Sandikci, Ö., & Ger, G. (2010). *Urban art and its influence on consumer perception: An exploratory study*. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(3), 455–472. <https://doi.org/10.1086/653430>

This work is the intellectual property of the author. Reproduction, citation, or distribution without proper credit is strictly prohibited. © Mohamed Touati, 2025.